

INFLUENCE OF THE POLYMER SURFACE LAYER ON THE ADHESION OF POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This work aims to point out the influence of the polymer surface layer on the adhesion of polymer matrix composites. To this end, correlations between surface parameters (chemistry, roughness, wettability, morphology...) resulting from several surface treatments or preparations and single lap shear tests were performed. The whole results show the usefulness of surface cleaning and the influence of the manufacturing process before the adhesion stage. Moreover, the use of peel ply surface treatment was also evidenced in terms of surface roughening and cleaning. Furthermore, most of the available surface treatments are limited by the cohesive failure occurring under the polymer surface layer at the fibre-polymer interface of the composite material. Hence, laser ablation is proposed as an alternative way to increase adhesion performance when compared to common surface treatments.

KEYWORDS: Adhesion, Surface characterisation, Surface treatment, Destructive tests, Peel ply, Laser ablation.

INTRODUCTION

Joining of composite materials with classical bonding techniques like riveting, bolting or screwing can lead to a dramatic additional weight of composite assemblies. Therefore, bonding composites using an adhesive layer appears to be the most suitable way from several points of view (economic, lighter, stronger, cheaper...).

In order to get highly performing assemblies, a special care must be brought to the surface preparation. Therefore numerous surface treatments are nowadays available [1-2] such as mechanical abrasion, plasma, grit-blasting, solvent etching and many others. Each of these techniques aims to improve a specific surface parameter such as surface roughness, chemical composition, surface cleaning....

The use of well adapted surface treatments can significantly improve adhesion performances; as a consequence of treatment efficiency, adhesive failure initially occurring between the adhesive layer and the composite surface is progressively shifted to a cohesive failure inside the material or in the bulk adhesive. In this last case of totally cohesive failure inside the material, the superficial polymer layer is partially removed as the material itself becomes the "weak point" of the assembly. In such a case, the use of classical surface treatments can not increase adhesion performances anymore.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Composite materials

Carbon/epoxy and glass/epoxy composites were manufactured by Hurel-Hispano Le Havre (SNECMA Group, FRANCE) using an autoclave process. The epoxy thermoset resin remains the same for both composites, only the fibre reinforcement (glass or carbon weaving) being different from one composite to another. Due to the high performances expected for aeronautic applications, the average fibre volume of these kinds of composite materials generally remains above 60%.

Surface analyses

The contact angle of sessile drops was measured using a GBX goniometer (Model *Digidrop++*). Uniform 3 μL drops of each liquid were carefully deposited at room temperature and humidity. Before taking any measurement of liquid droplet on a given surface, a kinetic study of the spreading was systematically carried out. Probe liquids were chosen with medium or high surface tensions (water, glycerol, formamide, diiodomethane and ethylene glycol) in order to yield an accurate measurement and analysis of the experimental contact angle. For each liquid used, the characterisation was attained within 10 to 20 droplets on 20 mm x 50 mm surfaces. The acid-base approach of Good-Van Oss-Chaudhury was used to assess both polar (γ^{AB}) and apolar (γ^{LW}) component of the total surface free energy (γ^{TOT}). The roughness was assessed by using a laser interferometer apparatus (*Altisurf 500*®). From all the available information deduced from analysis, the S_a parameter determined from surface reconstitution, was used instead of the more classical R_a as being more representative of rough anisotropic surfaces.

Both surface morphology assessment and study of the failure were examined with a scanning electron microscope *HITACHI S 3000 N* without surface metallization prior to observation within magnitude from 30 \times to 2500 \times .

Chemical analysis was led with ToF-SIMS (Time of Flight-Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry) apparatus: *TOF-SIMS IV (ION-TOF)*. Analytical measurements were performed on 50 x 50 μm^2 surfaces, at a depth lower than 10 Å (canon: Au-25kV). A semi-quantitative approach was attained by taking into account a reference for both positive and negative ions.

Complementary analyses were made with an ESCA (Electron Spectroscopy for Chemical Analysis) apparatus: *SPROBE (SSI)*. Analytical measurements were performed on a 300 μm x 1200 μm area, at a depth lower than 10 nm.

Single lap shear tests

Single lap shear tests were performed on 100 x 25 mm² composite specimens with a 12.5x25mm² bonding area. Glass/epoxy spacers were placed on one side of each bonded samples to assure perfect sample alignment during mechanical testing. Shear stress measurements were carried out at room temperature at 2 mm.min⁻¹ constant displacement rate on an *INSTRON 8802* apparatus with the *Merlin* software. The stress necessary to break the joint was determined from the stress/time curves, on five samples for each surface type, thus making it possible to calculate a representative average value and the typical error.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Bare surfaces

The use of a fluorinated film, as mould release agent to manufacture the composite material, leads to a very smooth and glossy surface ($R_a = 0.8\mu\text{m}$) exhibiting a very low surface free energy, as visible on table 1.

	Average roughness R_a (μm)	γ^{LW} ($\text{mJ}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$)	γ^{AB} ($\text{mJ}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$)	γ^{TOT} ($\text{mJ}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$)
Glass/epoxy	0.79 ($\pm 0,08$)	31.6 ($\pm 1,11$)	2.36 ($\pm 0,42$)	33.96 ($\pm 1,51$)
Carbon/epoxy	0.81 ($\pm 0,17$)	38.54 ($\pm 0,9$)	1.13 ($\pm 0,17$)	39.67 (± 1)

Table 1: Roughness and surface free energy of bare surfaces

The small gap between the carbon/epoxy and glass/epoxy composite surface free energy can be explained by a slight protrusion of fibre reinforcement near the surface. This leads to a higher polar surface for glass/epoxy composite when compared to the carbon/epoxy one. Finally, in such a case of smooth composite surface, surface properties are not only linked to the nature of the polymer surface layer, as fibre reinforcement also influences the resulting surface.

Moreover, weak wettabilities observed for both composites are also a result of the chemical pollution of fluorine species (30%), coming from the film release cloth as evidenced by ESCA analysis (Table 2).

	C	O	N	F	Si	S	O/C
Carbon/epoxy	56,4	8,1	1,5	32,2	1,8	-	0,14

Table 2: Chemical composition (%) of carbon/epoxy composite surface

As a result of both low wettability and surface pollution, single lap shear performances remain very low for both composites (290 and 400 daN for glass/epoxy and carbon/epoxy respectively).

Moreover both carbon/epoxy and glass/epoxy assemblies show a complete adhesive failure between the adhesive layer and the composite surface resulting from poor chemical and mechanical adhesion.

Peel ply surfaces

In order to eliminate the residual pollution previously evidenced, one of the widest spread surface treatments for composite surfaces was used. The peel ply treatment consists in a ply put onto the composite before curing; the removal of this ply prior to bonding allows getting a rough and clean surface [3], as visible on figure 1.

Figure 1: Surface reconstitution of glass/epoxy surface after peel ply treatment, as obtained by laser profilometry

Several peel plies have allowed to reach average roughness values between 10 to 20 μm . Corresponding surface cleaning efficiency and chemical modification can be demonstrated by using ToF-SIMS and contact angle analysis (Table 3-4).

	Water		Glycerol		Formamide		Ethylene-glycol		Diiodomethane	
	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b
Bare surface	74 (± 3)	85 (± 4)	75 (± 2)	78 (± 3)	42 (± 3)	56 (± 3)	55 (± 2)	59 (± 2)	45 (± 2)	56 (± 2)
Polyamide peel ply	43 (± 3)	44 (± 2)	38 (± 6)	34 (± 4)	24 (± 3)	23 (± 2)	7 (± 2)	7 (± 1)	6 (± 2)	7 (± 2)

^aCarbon/epoxy

^bGlass/epoxy

Table 3: Contact angle values (degrees) of bare and peel ply treated composite surface

All the contact angle values exhibit a sharp decrease resulting from peel ply use; this corresponds to an increase of surface free energy, mostly due to the roughening of the composite surface. Moreover, no differences in contact angle values are evidenced anymore between carbon/epoxy and glass/epoxy peel ply treated surfaces. This result clearly demonstrates that for such a treatment, the resulting surface morphology and properties are mainly related to the polymer matrix layer with no more influence of the fibre reinforcement.

	C ₆ H ₅	S ₀ ₃	NH ₄	SiC ₃ H ₉	CF	F	Cl	SiO ₂
Bare surface	-	16.4	1.2	37.5	2300	21103	465	2.25
Polyamide peel ply	64.4	0.3	23.8	25.8	5	20	19	0.07

Table 4: Semi quantitative analysis (ToF-SIMS) of bare and peel ply treated carbon/epoxy surface

The surface cleaning brought to the composite also explains this increase of surface free energy. Indeed, classical surface pollutants like fluorinated or siliconed species are completely removed from the composite surface after peel ply treatment (Table 4). Moreover, the surface cleaning and roughening clearly leads to an increase of single lap shear values, as depicted on figure 2. It then becomes possible to correlate single lap shear values with surface free energy; the surface homogenisation evidenced by contact angle measurements after peel ply treatment, also affects single lap shear test. This result confirms that with such a treatment, surface properties are only governed by the superficial polymer matrix layer, without anymore influence of fibre reinforcement.

Figure 2: Correlation of surface free energy and single lap shear values

The use of different peel plies allows determining the main parameters (roughness, chemical composition, peel ply morphology...) influencing the bond efficiency. As an example, the progressive increase of surface roughness with the same kind of polyester peel ply (arbitrary called PO1, PO2, PO3), gradually increases single lap shear values (figure 3).

Figure 3: Average surface roughness and single lap shear results of several assemblies treated with three different polyester peel plies

In this particular case, the failure mode is progressively shifted from a completely adhesive failure (PO1) to a mixed failure that becomes cohesive inside the composite material for PO3 sample.

Then, by selecting suitable peel ply parameters, it becomes possible to observe an optimum lap shear value corresponding to a complete cohesive failure inside the composite material (over 550 daN for both carbon/epoxy and glass/epoxy). In such a case the failure is related to the polymer layer removal between the fibre reinforcement and the composite surface. The material itself governs the limits of adhesion performances. One possible alternative is to bond the composite material directly to the fibre reinforcement, in order to avoid the cohesive failure between the superficial polymer layer and the fibre reinforcement.

Laser surfaces

In order to optimise the surface characteristics, laser treatment allows partial or complete removing of the superficial polymeric layer without affecting the fibre reinforcement [4-5]. By selecting suitable laser parameters (number of pulse, laser fluence), a fully controlled ablation of the superficial polymer layer can be obtained.

After only one laser pulse, a complete cleaning of the surface can be reached (table 5) as evidenced by the complete removal of fluorine pollution.

	C	O	N	F	Si	S	O/C
Bare surface	56.4	8.1	1.5	32.2	1.8	T	0.14
150 mJ/cm ² 1 pulse	80.4	12.5	5.6	0.7	0.5	0.5	0.16
150 mJ/cm ² 4 pulses	76.4	16.9	4.2	-	1.5	-	0.22
150 mJ/cm ² 10 pulses	78.6	15.9	3.6	-	1.1	-	0.2
150 mJ/cm ² 40 pulses	77.8	16	5.4	T	-	0.8	0.21
150 mJ/cm ² 400 pulses	77.4	16.9	5	-	-	0.7	0.22
500 mJ/cm ² 40 pulses	75.3	15.7	5.8	-	1.9	1.1	0.21

Table 5: Chemical composition (%) of epoxy matrix surface determined with ESCA analyses

In addition to that, the O/C ratio appears independent from laser parameters, as it remains at 0.21 on the epoxy matrix whatever the number of pulses and the laser fluence. Same results are obtained for the fibre reinforcement taken alone (results not shown).

Hence, based on the analysed results, three different ablation stages were evaluated: as described below (figure 4):

- Weak ablation: 150 mJ/m²-40 pulses
- Medium ablation: 150 mJ/m²- 400 pulses
- Total ablation: 500 mJ/m²-500 pulses

Figure 4: Surface profilometry of glass/epoxy surfaces with three different laser treatments
a) *Weak ablation ($S_a=0,6 \mu\text{m}$) ; b) Medium ablation ($S_a=13,1 \mu\text{m}$) ; C) Total ablation ($S_a=17,2 \mu\text{m}$)*

The weak ablation mode only provides a surface cleaning with no protrusion of fibre reinforcement or surface roughening. The medium ablation rate induces a quite rough surface which is composed of both fibre reinforcement and epoxy matrix (dark part on figure 4b). Finally, the total ablation mode exhibits a complete removal of matrix; the residual surface is then composed only of the fibre reinforcement's weaving.

Single lap shear tests of laser treated composites were investigated with an other adhesive with high performances, allowing a complete cohesive failure at the initial stage (table 6).

Treatment	Lap shear strength (daN)	Failure mode
Bare surface	642 ± 15	Cohesive in the material
150mJ/cm ² -1 pulse	647 ± 35	Cohesive in the material
150 mJ/cm ² -40 pulses	651 ± 21	Cohesive in the material
150 mJ/cm ² - 400 pulses	853 ± 25	Cohesive in the material Cohesive in the adhesive when bonded to the carbon fibre
500 mJ/cm ² - 500 pulses	671 ± 3	Cohesive in the material Ripping of superficial fibre

Table 6: Lap shear value and failure mode of laser treated carbon/epoxy composites

As illustrated in table 6, the cohesive failure is observed for all assemblies whatever the surface preparation, at least at the initial stage. Consequently, both the untreated surface and the low treated ones (1 pulse and 40 pulses) exhibit the same lap shear value. In this case, the crack propagation is not dependent of the surface treatment since it occurs at the fibre-matrix interface of the composite. The use of an excimer laser treatment then appears particularly well-adapted to such a situation as this surface treatment completely changed the nature of the adherent.

The use of the 400 pulses treatment shows that the slight fibre protruding, leads to a great increase of lap shear value (over 850 daN). Considering the failure mode, one can evidence the shifting of the rupture from cohesive inside the material to cohesive inside the adhesive layer. Moreover, the cohesive failure inside the adhesive takes place in the area where the adhesive layer is directly linked to the fibre reinforcement. This result clearly indicates that the adhesive provides a high performance quality of bonding toward the fibre reinforcement.

Finally, the lap shear value measured for the totally ablated surfaces assembly is 671 daN, the decrease of this lap shear value on the extreme laser treatment may be explained looking at the failure location. SEM observations allows to demonstrate that reinforcing fibres are completely ripped off the composite material. As such a phenomenon does not occur for lower number of pulses, one can deduce that the laser treatment used for total ablation actually creates a kind of weak boundary layer between the superficial fibres exposed to the laser beam. Owing to the total ablation occurring at the composite surface, the remaining fibres are not linked to the bulk material anymore, thus explaining the premature rupture for such totally ablated samples. The interest of polymer matrix removal to get fibre protrusion to enhance adhesion performances of composite surface assemblies is consequently limited by the establishment of a weak boundary layer.

CONCLUSION

The different surface treatments evaluated allowed to bring some highlights upon the main parameters governing adhesion abilities and performances of composite materials. Indeed, surface pollution, coming from manufacturing process have clearly harmed the adhesive behaviour of the resulting composite assembly. Then, the use of peel plies treatments allowed complete surface cleaning and roughening of the composite. The interest of such treatments in surface homogenisation and lap shear performances was clearly demonstrated.

Furthermore, when peel ply parameters are suitably selected, this surface treatment, like many others, is limited by the cohesive failure occurring in the composite at the fibre-matrix interface. Then, laser treatment provides a complete changing of the composite surface as it allows reaching the fibre reinforcement itself. By removing the superficial polymer layer, one can clearly observe a great increase of lap shear performances. Best results are not coming from the totally ablated surface, because laser treatment can create a superficial weak boundary layer made of fibre reinforcement. Therefore one can obtain a suitable bond, if laser ablation conditions are carefully determined.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by Hurel-Hispano Le Havre (SNECMA Group, FRANCE), Région Haute-Normandie (FRANCE) and the European Fund for Regional Development (FEDER). Special thanks go to the “CRITT Analyses et Surfaces” team (Louviers, FRANCE) for roughness assessment. Finally we appreciated the help of members of Plate Forme Technologique (Le Havre University) for the use of the mechanical testing machine and SEM studies. The authors dedicate the present paper to the memory of regretted Prof. TK Wang.

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